

Quality of Work Life and Human Resource Management in Business Process Management (BPM) Companies in India

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ABSTRACT

Quality of work life plays an important role in the present global business environment to improve the organizational performance and excellence in terms of achieving profitability and productivity to reach the organizational goals. The work life is based on the Person's mentality and the psychological factors. Authors, people of organization, psychologists and also the management consultants agreed to give a 100% perfect definition based on their experience and observations. The happiness and behavior of the employees is measured by their way of life.

The employees life style is determined with individual characteristics and individual characteristics of need pattern, tolerance of every issue in organization, work principles, values, abilities and skills of the employees.

People behavior and work life balance usually varies from person to person. Reaching higher position will satisfy the mental urges. Engaging with the given work will also be helpful for balancing the personal life satisfaction.

Organizational trainings and career development will be helpful to precise the quality of work life Appreciations, and Motivation, are the most important needs. It is important factor of work life status improvement. More recognition in job needs to be appreciated. Employees must be rewarded for his extra work Development and work skills. At the same time lethargic and lazy employees must be penalized. This will be helpful in motivating employees.

INTRODUCTION:

Nowadays in this competitive world every employee needs to play a vital role both in work and family.

Earlier days they performed few common jobs but now they are into several differ sectors.

This has become difficult for the employees to manage both work and family. While trying to balance their life in their several roles, any imbalance leads to stress. Because of this stress factor there are several organizations addressing their working employees with several HR policies.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Organizations today are focusing on HR policies and Practices for making decision. Employees performance is analyzed based on their deliverables within their jobs and also, Management decision with respect to hiring, training, performance analysis. Decision are based on individual perspective rather than considering past data and future requirements – known and unknown.

Workforce planning is done keeping in view the new projects and bench requirements

Training is planned based on the current challenges and not on the basis of accurate past data and future requirements of training needs.

Processes are designed and developed temporarily and based on current challenges only. Performance appraisal is done based on scores and manager's intuition. Organization is not paying attention to curtail down High attrition and retention or replacement is the only solution.

This research study had focused on the relevance of design of HR policies and strategies, how it had impacted on the improvement of behavior of employees by developing a strategic model with a selected Business Process Management (BPM) organization in Greater Hyderabad.

HR issues:

- To improve business performance with the help of data based decisions
- To increase individual and organizational productivity
- Curtail attrition and increase retention
- Improve employee performance
- Process improvement

training and development, performance management, statutory and payroll management is very important.

It is an important function that deals with providing employee support in terms of managing people, issues, motivation and bringing the best culture for employees to work.

MANAGEMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES:

The development of management resources like human beings by way of best selection process,

The responsibility of HRM has moved from earlier days of personnel management which was restricted to shop floor hiring and managing the unions. The present HRM focuses on productivity of every employees and aligning the same to the organizational goals and objectives,

uses employee data from work history and make predictions related to employees. Example – every organization will have attrition and it tends to loose few of the best performers due to various reasons. Using HR analytics tools and data we can predict at early stage which employee is looking for job change before it is late.

Main focus of HRM

- Talent acquisition
- Competency based hiring
- Training and Development
- PMS
- Reward and recognition
- Payroll Management
- Employee engagement and retention

There are number of reason why an employee leaves and how they can be retained by giving them role, designation, better pay package, advanced training etc which can be retrieved from historical data.

HR analytics is an approach to HR function which brings strategic tools and analytical data in the areas of HRM for improving employee performance and increase overall business performance.HR analytics

Life Style

Knowledge Management
 E-HRM practices
 Relationship management
 Leadership Management
 Innovation and Creativity
 HR Policies
 Welfare policies

Fig 1.1: Human Capabilities

Performance of every employee can be another example where HR Analytics plays vital role, performance earlier was only considered as job related performance but that is not true Manager used to rate his subordinate on his role and responsibility and gauge his performance, but the fact is there are other parameters which are not considered by the manager for reasons for low performance like past experience, qualification, skill and competency.

By using historic data, the reason for low performance can be measured and it includes:

- a. Lack of Competency and skill
- b. Past experience
- c. Lack of training and supervision
- d. Number of trainings attended
- e. Lack of desired skill and qualification

Based on the above HR analytical data manager will get to know the exact reason for low performance and can plan accordingly the future course of action for his subordinates.

Quality of work life and HR analytics:

Poor hiring decisions can lead to a disaster in any organization in terms of productivity and performance. Example – if you hire 20 people and 10 failed due to mismatch of skill sets you will again have to hire new people. With the help of HR Analytics you will not make the mistake of wrong hiring.

Training plays a major role in improving ones efficiency. Wrong training can cost very heavily to

the organization in terms of time and money. HR Analytics help with providing accurate data on training needs and the patterns which if adopted earlier, more accurate and need based training can be given to improve skill sets

Retention comes with one of the biggest challenge for every organization. Employee attrition can be easily captured with the help of HR Analytics. It tells why people leave organization – whether it is for better growth opportunity, better salary, working environment or job miss match. Historic data is recorded, monitored and produced before the management for taking relevant decision for employee retention. Example, Employee Satisfaction Survey, Employee Opinion Survey, Exit interviews etc , these statistics help management in retaining the best talent.

Identify top performers, with the help of huge data stacked in HR department, and this leads to better decision making in terms of promotion, increment, job role change etc.

Measure employee Satisfaction at Job: HR analytics will help you to get relevant data to measure how employees feel happy about their work place and what can keep them engaged.

Employee absenteeism, HR analytics can get you solutions as to why employee remain absent to duty by analyzing his / her past record of absenteeism. It will give you the analysis of reason for remaining absent and helps the organization to come out with better engagement plans.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study the Business Process Management Companies employee life in terms of quality and behavioral aspects
- 2) To analyze the factors affecting on the work life balance of the employees.
- 3) To evaluate the employee performance and its impact on organizational performance.
- 4) Strategic factors and its contribution to improve the organizational work culture.
- 5) To study the employee job satisfaction and its relevance to motivational aspects.

- 6) To suggest efficient and effective strategies to improve the BPM Companies performance and Return on Investment (ROI).

Hypothesis:

- 1) Ho: Positive relation of organizational work culture and employee quality of work life.
H1: Negative relation of organizational work culture and employee quality of work life.
- 2) Ho: Positive Relation between quality of work life and organizational performance.
H1: Negative Relation between quality of work life and organizational performance.
- 3) Ho: Organizational HR Policies helps to improve the moral of employees.
H1: Organizational HR Policies could not help to improve the moral of employees
- 4) Ho: Employees motivation helps to improve the job satisfaction.
H1: Employees motivation could not help to improve the job satisfaction.
- 5) Ho: The 360 degree appraisal system of HR helps to improve the performance evaluation and framing the best remuneration and promotional policies.
H1: The 360 degree appraisal system of HR could not help to improve the performance evaluation and framing the best remuneration and promotional policies.

Data Collection

The research data is collected from various dimensions of QWL. These dimensions are re-categorized into the major components of QWL – Job Satisfaction, Job Autonomy and Work Life Balance. A Questionnaire was designed for the purpose of this study based on the derived dimensions of QWL. The questionnaire was administered to 500 employees based on a convenience sampling from various BPM companies in Hyderabad.

Sampling

The sample had taken on the basis of stratified sampling consisting of 5 Organizations representing from Health and well being, Banking and Financial services, Hotels and restaurants, IT services and others.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Table: 1 Work cultures of BPM Companies

Variable	Factor
Company image and public acceptance	.658
Employing belongingness	.644
Employee motivation	.634
Loyal to the organization	.562
Working long periods	.548
Commitment of employees	.662

The work culture aspects of BPM companies such as image, motivation, loyalty and commitment aspects have good impact on the quality aspects of human beings working in the companies as shown in table 1

Table 2: Job satisfaction

Variable	Factor
Employee achievement and appreciation	.682
Freedom to make decisions	.642
Technology orientation	.602
No discrimination on social, rational, religion	.578
Person's involvement in job	.578
Good quality products and services	.572
Clear authority and responsibility of the job	.556
Good human relations	.462
Research and development contribution	.462

Table 3.2 reveals the significant attributes of job satisfaction variables such as Employee achievement and appreciation, Freedom to make decisions, Technology orientation, authority and responsibility, Good human relations and Research and development contribution factors are positively correlated with BPM Companies' performance.

Table 3: Developing skills and abilities

Variable	Factor
Scope for professional growth	.582
Continuous learning environment	.571
Skill developing program	.654
Environment to higher studies and work shops	.542
Participation in seminars and work shops	.542

The skills and abilities of BPM employees i.e Scope for professional growth (.582), Continuous learning environment(.571), Skill developing program(.654), Environment to higher studies and workshops(.542), Participation in seminars and workshops (.542). All variable factor loadings are above .5 and that these factors are more relevant for developing employee skills to achieve quality of work and job satisfaction.

Table: 4.Training and developing

Variable	Factor
Continuous on the training facility	5.72
Training to improve the job performance	.592
Skills for job performance	.586
Experts interaction	.569
Support for job efficiency	.564
Continuous evaluation of employees' performance	.520
Providing executive training	.652

Table 5 shows that there will be a qualitative improvement of employees through training and development facilities to improve the skills and expertise relating to job performance.

Table: 5 Composition policy

Variable	Factor
Sound wage policy	.672
Reckoning efforts and contribution	.556
Performance appraisal	.576
Good promotions policy	.436
Rewards linked to performance	.646
Salary package with abilities	.582
Retirement benefits plans	.562

Table 5 presents that the compensation policies are much relevant to base policy, promotional aspects and retirement benefits. The selected BPM Companies employees stated that there is a good scope and performance rewards are extended by these companies to encourage the work force.

Table: 6 Work environment

Variable	Factor
Good work facilities	.643
Resources work related problems	.592
Fair work load distribution	.586
Resources standards	.575
Scientific work scheduling	.559
No problem of unions	.542
Higher work facilities	.477

Work environment of selected BPM Companies in respect of work facilities, resource aspects, work scheduling indicated a qualitative improvement of employee performance as presented in the above table

Table: 7 Sincerity and commitment

Variable	Factor
Commitment to work commitment	.643
Sincerity in work performance	.636
Commitment towards performances	.642
Commitment to protect organization policies	.563

The sincerity and commitment variables relevant to work performance have shown a good improvement in the work culture of selected BPM Companies' employees as presented in Table 7

Table 8: Social Culture

Variable	Factor
Good social relations	.670
Occasional social meeting	.556
Resolving disputes internally	.548
Awareness about job and role	.445
Family member support	.643
Company support	.643

Table 8 represents the social culture aspects in respect of social relations, social meetings, resolving disputes, family support in respect of job satisfaction and employee performance of BPM Companies have a positive relation in terms of improving quality of work life.

The study had found the quality of work life and job satisfaction related to behavioral aspects and its impact on organizational performance. Motivational aspects have significant impact on organizational success and achievements. The study has developed a better work life balance model by considering relevant variables such as work culture, motivational, environmental, innovative thinking and knowledge management factors.

Most of the employees in BPM companies are satisfied to do work with pleasure. The organization provide favorable climate to employees in their work life.

All the employees feel that the performance appraisal is to know the knowledge level of the employee in the

organization and to analyze the systems for further development of employee.

REFERENCES:

1. Bora B, Das S, Murthy V. Quality of work life-a literature review. *Int J Manag Soc Sci* 2015;3:106-15.3.
2. Fapohunda MT. An evaluation of the perceptions and experiences of quality of work life in Nigeria. *Int J Acad Res Manag* 2013;4:97-8.4.
3. Hamidi F, Mohamadi B. Teachers' quality of work life in secondary schools. *Int J Vocat Tech Educ* 2012;4:1-5.5.
4. Ganapathi R. A study on quality of work life of workers in construction industry in Madurai district. *JManag Res Anal* 2016;3:63-6.6.
5. Gayathiri R, Ramakrishnan L. Quality of work life - Linkage with job satisfaction and performance. *Int J Bus Manag Invent* 2013;2:1-8.